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Increasing Students' Motivation in Learning English

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to increase the motivation to learn English in ninth grade students of Hazrat Waliar (AS) school. This research was carried out with the participatory action research method in three dimensions of diagnosis, implementation and evaluation of results in seven stages for 3 months and with the participation of 50 students of the above middle school, located in East Azerbaijan province - Tasuj city in the academic year 1402-1403. In this research work, the researcher was able to identify the reasons for the low motivation of learners in learning English by examining and analyzing the information in the first stage, which was collected through observation, review of documents and interviews. Among the most important reasons are the boring atmosphere of the classrooms, the lack of use of modern methods in education, having difficulty in memorizing English words, etc. First, with the help of the school counselor, the researcher tried to eliminate the factors of lack of concentration in the class. Then, by grouping classes, using virtual environment for education, using music in education and playing games and holding competitions, the second step was taken in order to increase the learning motivation of learners. After examining the second data and evidence, the results indicated an increase in the motivation to learn English among students. So that with the implementation of this research, students' participation in the class increased and their performance in tests improved compared to before.

Keywords: *Motivation - Middle School Students - Strengthening English Language Learning - Reasons for Academic Weakness and Backwardness in English Language Lessons - Creative Teaching*

Introduction

Today, mastering the English language has become an essential skill for everyone. In addition to the fact that this language is a main and general language for communication all over the world and is considered the first language of the world, it is also important in all scientific, political, economic, military, etc. fields in the world. In other words, if someone wants to get acquainted with the world's modern sciences and the knowledge of the people of other countries, they must learn the English language. Imam Khomeini's words: "There was no need for a (foreign) language before. Today it is needed. The living languages of the world should be part of the schools' advertising program. Today is not like yesterday when our voice did not go out of Iran. Today we can be in Iran and Advertise everywhere in the world in another language." It is printed at the beginning of all language textbooks, which is a proof of the importance of learning English. Learning English as a foreign language is a very complex process. In other words, language learners not only need to learn the pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar of this language, but also need to learn its culture. In fact, it can be said that many factors affect the learning or failure of learners in language learning; Such as motivation, intelligence, talent, etc. Among these factors, it is said that the motivation of English language learners plays a vital role in the foreign language learning process. Various definitions have been made of motivation, one of the most comprehensive of which is the following definition: motivation is the force that creates, maintains and guides behavior. Moreno (2010) has also provided this definition for learning motivation: "psychological processes that guide and maintain students' behavior in the direction of learning." Saif (2018) says about the effect of motivation on learning:

If the students are disinterested in the lesson (have a low level of motivation), they will not pay attention to the teacher's explanations, they will not do their homework seriously, and finally, they will not make much progress. But if they are interested in the lesson (have a high level of motivation), they will listen carefully to the teacher's explanations, they will do their homework seriously, and they will look for more information about the subject and they will make a lot of progress.

According to what was said, the importance of learning English and the role of motivation on learning is quite obvious. But when I first entered an English class in a school, some students asked why we should learn English at all? This lesson is not useful to us. This view is especially common among students in rural areas who do not have enough facilities and are not interested in studying. Since learning English is very difficult for most people and students who do not have enough motivation and interest in learning this subject, the task of the language teacher is to correct this view and increase their motivation to learn English. Therefore, by reviewing researches and numerous articles written about the effect of motivation on learning English, I set out to increase students' learning motivation and identify strategies for this important action. In fact, my goal, which I am faced with the low motivation of Hazrat Waliasr (AS) school students to learn English, is to make them learn this language with full enthusiasm and not by force; Because studying by force will not have any lasting effect and my goal is for students to learn English in depth. Dorney's (1998) belief that "it is the motivation that initiates learning and the driving force to continue the learning process, which is sometimes considered a boring process." It also confirms the point mentioned. In this research, the important questions that are investigated are why some students have low learning motivation to learn English? Why do students neglect to learn English even though it is widely used in today's modern life? How to improve and increase this low motivation?

Description of the existing situation and problem statement

After two sessions since the beginning of the academic year 1402-1403, I realized that a large number of students are not very interested in learning English. Actually, due to the fact that from the end of 1398 to Mehr 1401, the trainings were virtual, the students had fallen academically. This type of education had the worst effect on these students; Their self-confidence and motivation to learn had decreased and it can be said that these factors were one of the reasons for their failure in English lessons. Based on my observations in the English classes of this school, to check the situation of the students in the English language course, in addition to the fact that the students had low motivation and self-confidence, their level in English was very low. In the second session of the English language lesson, ninth grade students openly stated that they blame their previous year's teacher and her teaching method for this incident. Of course, I warned them that learning is self-contained and they should search within themselves for the reason for their weakness in English. Wankins, Carnell Vlaugé (2007) also consider the source of learning in the learner and consider external aids only as facilitating factors. They have said about this: No one can learn for you. However, others may be able to help you learn by providing the right environment or talking to you. Therefore, the learner is always at the heart of the learning process.

In general, the academic status of the students was not good at all. Their motivation to learn was very low and they did not show interest in learning. During my observations, they were constantly looking at the wall clock above the classroom board, arguing with me about their homework, they did not volunteer for any activities, they played with their stuff while teaching and did not pay attention to what the teacher said. Considering that about 90% of ninth grade students were not able to answer the teacher's questions, I realized that their level in this lesson is very low and if they don't study and learn English seriously, they will definitely face problems in their final exam. This concern made me think of a solution. Therefore, I tried to collect information about this issue so that I can find the root of the problem in a precise way and to solve it based on the methods and solutions recorded in reliable sources as well as a series of creative methods.

Methodology

The current research method is action research, which is one of the qualitative research approaches. Action research is a process that improves education through change, and its results are used to improve the teaching-learning process and change the existing unfavorable situation to a relatively favorable one. The statistical population of this research was 74 students of Hazrat Waliasr (AS) middle school, located in Tasouj city, of which 50 were willing to cooperate with the researcher. After reading the books, articles and research results related to the research topic, semi-structured interview tools, document review and observation were used to collect the required data and information.

Data Collection (Preliminary Evidence)

In the current research, to collect data, the researcher used several combined methods of observation, review of existing documents and interviews. The collection of information and data in this stage was done through the following:

Observing the behavior of learners in classrooms

During the course of the classes, some cases were observed in the behavior of the students, which could indicate the low motivation of the learners to learn English. These include:

- Entertaining themselves with other activities such as playing with stationery, scrawling on the bench, whispering to classmates during the teacher's teaching process.

- Little participation and even non-participation of some students
- Arguing with the teacher about removing or reducing homework
- Not having a clear goal to learn English at school
- Drowsiness of students in the classroom
- Repeatedly looking at the wall clock
- Unwillingness to repeat words after the English teacher
- Unwillingness to answer the teacher's questions.

Document review

In order to know the performance of the students in the previous year and to use this information to compare with their performance in the final exams of the current semester, their scores in the English course were observed and analyzed.

The average scores of the students of each grade in the last year's final English exams are listed separately in the following table:

Grade	9.1	9.2	9.3
the number of students	25	24	25
The average scores in the last year's final English exam	17/16	17/34	18/11

Interview

In the first step, a semi-structured interview was conducted with the school principal, teachers and parents of the students, in order to identify their points of view regarding the low motivation and weakness of the students in learning English. The school principal and teachers pointed out: virtual education was not well received by students due to problems such as low internet speed, problems and weaknesses of the Shad application, lack of access of some students to tools such as personal smartphones, tablets and computers. On the other hand, the teachers could not make a reliable evaluation of the students' academic status and identify the problems and weaknesses of students in each lesson and take action to solve them. Because the results of class evaluations did not have the necessary accuracy due to the cheating that was done by the students.

Some parents also mentioned that they couldn't afford to provide tablets and smartphones for all their children, so their children could not participate in all virtual classes. Of course, they also acknowledged that some students come to school because they are afraid of their parents or to avoid being ridiculed by others for dropping out, and they are not very interested in studying.

After hearing the opinions of the principal, teachers and parents of the students, I decided to establish a good emotional relationship with all the students and gain their trust so that I can hear the reasons for their weakness in the English language lesson from their own words and then take the necessary actions. Each of them had their own reasons for not studying and academic failure, but there were also common points among these opinions, such as:

- **Boredom in the classrooms:** considering that the training was virtual for a year and several months, according to the students' statements, the routine of the classes was very boring. They have been required to be in the Shad application every day at a certain time and then their teacher sent them

educational videos from other channels, and after thanking the teacher for sending the content, the class ended.

- **Disinterest in learning English:** This has many reasons; Including not having a specific goal in learning English, the inability of the educational system to create motivation and purpose in learners, learner's internal fear (of making mistakes in language classes, etc.), negative insinuations from people around (what happened to the others who studied, most university graduates are unemployed and ...)
- **Not having enough practice and repetition:** About 99% of the students said that the average time they spend each week studying and practicing English is less than one hour, which is not enough time to learn English.
- **Low quality of virtual education:** Considering that the previous language teacher did not make any efforts to produce educational content, so they used the content produced by other English language teachers. According to the students themselves, these contents did not match their level and their needs and were of low quality.
- **Lack of application of new and innovative methods in teaching English:** The students complained that the GTM teaching method made them bored in the classroom, because they did not have a chance to participate in the classroom. Their role in the classroom was only to note down the teacher's words and memorize the translation and grammar rules of the English language.
- **Lack of access to language institutes:** Considering that a significant number of students are from rural areas and the distance between the village and the city center is relatively large, despite the motivation they had to participate in the language classes of the institutes, these students could not attend these classes, and this caused losing interest in learning English. Because they believed, only students who have facilities can succeed in this field.
- **Ignoring the individual differences of learners:** They said that their teacher does not pay attention to the students who have a low level and presents all the content based on the level of the smart students in this lesson, so they do not want to attend English classes because it does not match their level and does not meet their needs.
- **Students' difficulty in memorizing English vocabulary:** The students mentioned that English words are very hard to keep in mind and when they memorize new words and expressions, they are unable to recall them after a short period of time.
- **Insufficient instructional time:** 2 hours per week are dedicated to teaching English at school. According to the students, due to the lack of time, a lot of content is presented to them in this little time, and on the other hand, there is no opportunity to error correction in the class; These factors ultimately lead to students' tiredness and loss of interest in learning English.

Literature review

Due to the importance of the impact of motivation on learning and academic progress of students, many researches have been conducted on the relationship between motivation and learning, the role of motivation on learning and other similar issues, both inside and outside the country. In order to complete the information and use the ideas and experiences of other researchers, these studies were examined. In the following, the findings of some of the most important researches are mentioned.

Kaveh (2009) in a research entitled "Motivation and Learning" reached the conclusion that the behavior and performance of students in education is different according to the level of motivation of their progress. Motivation is a very important factor and often the most important condition for learning, and its importance is even greater than general intelligence. Rahmatbar et al.(2015) also concluded that without motivation, learning is not possible and where there is no learning, there is no teaching. Motivated students are eager to learn and hardworking. Students are more successful in subjects for which they are more

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motivated. Piri Naruni (2017) in a research covered the "increasing the interest of 9th grade students in English language and learning it". In this research, which was conducted with 23 students, the reasons for the disinterest of these students in the English language (fear of the teacher, unattractive classes, unattractive textbooks, etc.) were identified and by using methods such as using flash cards, smart classes, various competitions and various related videos, etc. English language learning in students improved and strengthened. Farsani et al. (2014) also conducted a research entitled "Investigation of ways to increase students' motivation and its effect on English language learning". The results of the research showed that there is a significant positive relationship between internal motivation and its components with the English language, and this type of motivation has the lion's share in learning English. Shafiei and Karami (2019) during a research entitled "Students' academic motivation" reached the conclusion that when students' motivation decreases, academic performance and academic progress will definitely decrease, so one of the duties of teachers is to Before doing anything, create the necessary motivation in students; If they succeed in doing that, they will pave the way for teaching and learning in students.

Data analysis

Observing the behavior of students in English classes showed that students do not concentrate in the classroom and their desire to learn and participate in the class is very low. Examining the documents (2nd semester report cards of the students in 1402) indicated that most of the students did not perform well in the final exam of the English course. This poor performance can indicate their academic weakness in the English language course. The analysis of the interviews conducted with the teaching staff of the school, parents and students showed that their motivation to learn English is very low. The roots of this low motivation are the problems of virtual education (poor internet connection and slow speed of Shad application, lack of access to smart phones for some students), boring classrooms, lack of using modern methods in teaching English, lack of practice and repetition, having trouble in memorizing English vocabulary and expressions, ignoring the individual differences of learners in education, lack of access to language institutes, low quality of virtual education and insufficient instructional time allocated to English in the weekly school schedule. All these factors are considered as obstacles to students' learning, which ultimately reduce their motivation to learn English.

Choosing temporary solutions to the problem

Studying the research done in this field shows that not having enough motivation to learn is the most important obstacle to learning English correctly. In order to improve English language learning, the motivation to learn English should be increased in language learners. Most students are not interested in learning this language and do not motivate themselves to learn and only think about passing this course; Therefore, because they are not interested and do not listen willingly in class, they do not learn anything, and if they learn, they quickly forget because they are tired and hate repeating it. Considering the results of the data analysis and by studying the books and researches, the researcher came to the conclusion that the topic of motivation can be investigated in two categories: inside and outside the classroom (Betman and Crant, 2004). Before any action, it should be considered that the good and appropriate behavior of the teacher with the students is the most important point in creating motivation. The teachers must use all their power to be friendly with the students and gain their trust. In this case, the teacher wins the students over the processes of learning and reach the goals.

In the second step, after establishing a close relationship between the teacher and the students, actions should be taken to provide all the conditions for learning English correctly. Actions such as:

✓ **Eliminating Distraction Factors in the Classroom:**

One of the most important factors that prevent language learning is lack of concentration, because a student who does not have concentration cannot learn the material. This concentration depends on the following factors:

- Hunger
- Fatigue and insomnia
- Learning environment
- Family issues

To resolve all these issues, it is better to ask the school counselor for help.

✓ **Grouping of Students:**

One of the effective methods of teaching is the formation of educational groups in the classroom. Students in groups can discuss together, do exercises together, solve problems, correct errors and participate in group competitions. This makes the classroom atmosphere more intimate and positive, and language learners can help each other in increasing productivity and learning level.

✓ **Using Virtual Learning Environments**

Social networks can be the best way of communication for language learners. By using social networks, you can communicate with students outside of class hours. By placing attractive educational posts, the teacher can make students eager to participate in the class and learn the material. In this way, they will receive a part of English language education through social networks.

✓ **Using Educational Music and Videos in the Classroom**

Some cartoon animations, funny movies and English music can have the best effect on learning English. Since most language learners are interested in these things, the teacher can encourage learners to participate in the class and learn more by using a collection of the most influential movies and music. Examples of different animations can be used according to the language level of the learners.

✓ **Teaching English through Games and Entertainment**

Many people believe that games and entertainment can only be effective for teaching language to children, but the latest research in this field shows that one of the best ways, especially in the field of learning new words and English conversation, can be used for all age groups is to use attractive games. Pantomime is one of the funniest games that can be used in language classes. In this way, language learners are forced to look for the English meanings of the most frequently used words. Family name game, which is one of the most attractive games for us Iranians, can be useful for language learners. In younger age groups, puppet games are very effective. Learners can act out daily English conversations as a puppet game. This method makes language learning very enjoyable.

✓ **Running a Competition in the Classroom**

Competition is one of the most exciting methods of teaching in the classroom. By holding educational competitions in the class, the teacher can encourage the language learners to participate in the class discussions, apply what they have learned, and as a result have more effective learning. This competition can be in all parts of learning English. Group competitions are among the most attractive methods of teaching in the classroom.

✓ **Presentation of Course Materials from Simple to Difficult**

Presenting course materials from simple to difficult makes students succeed in learning simple materials first, and this initial success increases their motivation and readiness to learn more difficult materials.

Validation of the Selected Solution

In order to ensure the implementation of the chosen solution and gain more credibility in this field, the opinions of other English teachers, principal and school counselor were used and their opinions were taken into consideration to strengthen and better implement the temporary solutions. Project validation criteria are:

- Approval of the solutions by the principal and the school counselor
- Effectiveness and ability to implement some solutions in other courses
- Discussion with several experienced English language teachers about the existing plan.

Implement a Temporary Solution to Solve the Problem

Considering the important roots of the low motivation of the learners, which were: the boring classrooms, the lack of application of modern methods in education, ignoring the individual differences of the learners, having trouble in memorizing English words and the insufficient instructional time devoted to English in the weekly school schedule; The researcher decided to use all the proposed solutions in combination. The steps of implementing the solutions are as follows:

Eliminating Factors of Lack of Concentration and Providing Effective Methods of Learning English

In the first stage, by providing a suitable platform, a meeting was held with the cooperation of the school counselor to present important points to increase students' concentration in the classroom. Also, in this meeting, effective study tips and techniques and effective methods of learning English were also presented to the audience.

Grouping students of each grade

In the second stage, the students of each class were grouped. Each group consisted of 3 to 4 students and the level of students in each group was also heterogeneous (in each group, a combination of elementary and intermediate level students was used, so that students with a higher level could help weaker students in learning English). The purpose of grouping the students was that they discuss and talk together, do exercises together, solve problems and participate in group competitions, and the shy and quiet students are encouraged to be active. In these groups, activities such as studying and translating interesting English texts, doing tasks in groups and role play were done in order to help students learn.

Using virtual environment for education

Considering that the time allotted for teaching and learning English in school was not enough, in the third stage, it was decided to use the capacity of the Shad application to provide videos recorded by the teacher and supplementary contents of the textbook. The students were asked to carefully study the videos and contents in the group before each session and raise their questions and problems in the classroom. It was also suggested to them that if they use social networks such as Instagram, they should try to publish their posts in English and write their comments in English under each other's posts.

Using Music in Teaching and Playing Games and Holding Competitions

In the last stage, considering that the students complained about using the GTM method in teaching English and it was boring for them to memorize the translation and grammar rules, the use of educational music, teaching English through games and entertainment in the classroom and also holding competitions, was widely and well received by the students, and considering the reward to the top group by adding a score to their formative assessment led to an increase in the desire and motivation of language learners to participate in learning activities.

Presentation of Course Materials from Simple to Difficult

In order to increase the success of students in learning English, in teaching the content of textbooks, it was tried to present the content from simple to difficult level. When students were successful in learning simple content, their motivation and desire to learn difficult content increased.

Monitoring of the Solution

In order to ensure the correct implementation of the solutions and their effectiveness, there was a need for experienced and qualified people to supervise the implementation of the solutions. Therefore, a group of administrators, academic advisors and English teachers were selected as observers and critics of the research. Each solution was approved by them before implementation, and their opinions were taken into consideration to strengthen and improve the chosen solutions; During the implementation of each of the mentioned five stages, the criticisms presented by this group played an important role in the successful implementation of the research.

Gathering New Data (second stage evidence)

In the evidence section, problems such as boring classrooms, not using modern methods in education, ignoring the individual differences of learners, etc. were raised. The changes obtained after the implementation of the selected solutions are as follows:

1- Observation

During and after the implementation of the solutions, the following were observed in the students' behavior:

- Increasing the participation of all students in activities such as role playing, classroom activities and extracurricular activities.
- increasing students' enthusiasm during English classes.
- Increasing students' willingness to ask questions from the teacher and their desire to answer the teacher's questions.
- Reducing the absence of students in English classes.

2- Document review

Examining the available documents (English language test papers) indicated the improvement of students' scores in this course compared to the last year.

Grade	9.1	9.2	9.3
the number of students	25	24	25
The average scores in the last year's final English test	17/16	17/34	18/11
Average scores in the final English exam of the first semester of 1402-1403	18/32	18/68	19/01

3- Interview

The interviews conducted with the principal and English teacher of the school clearly showed that the motivation to learn English among the students has increased. According to the principle's statement, the students asked the teachers of other courses to implement such plans. According to conversations with several parents, students study English seriously at home and devote a lot of time to learning and practicing this lesson. The students themselves were also happy with the positive and enjoyable atmosphere that the implementation of this plan in the classroom had provided for them.

The final report

In the course of this research, with the help of the school's teaching staff, parents and students themselves, the researcher identified the main reasons for the students' low learning motivation. In the next step, by studying related books and articles, after validating the selected solutions by experienced and qualified people, she implemented her research plan. The information collected in the second stage indicated an increase in the motivation to learn English and an improvement in the performance of students in formative assessments as well as the final test of English compared to last year. The findings of this research showed that motivation is the most important factor in the academic progress of students in the English language course. Considering the importance of motivation in learning, it is suggested to the respected colleagues to create a positive atmosphere in the classroom and use relationships based on love, respect and mutual trust between the teacher and the student in order to increase the internal motivation of the students and if there is a decrease in the motivation in students, find its reason and take into account the characteristics and individual differences of students and the facilities available in the school, to solve its possible causes.

Grouping students, using musical content related to the content of textbooks, and holding contests and games in the classroom are among the strategies that can be implemented in all schools and have an important impact on the quality of learning and increasing the motivation to learn English among students.

Suggestions and solutions

Considering the results obtained in this research, some suggestions and solutions are presented as follows:

Suggestion to Educational Authorities:

Considering the importance and impact of motivation on the academic performance of students, which was mentioned in this research, it is expected that the respected authorities will provide the necessary platform for English language teachers so that they can share their experiences and effective solutions in order to increase the motivation to learn English. The importance of this is due to the fact that creating motivation among students and trying to make them interested in learning increases the efficiency of

language classes. The researches of Knowles et al. (2000) and Grolik (1987) also show better performance and higher quality of learning if motivation is created.

Suggestion to Dear Colleagues

According to the findings of numerous researches, when students' motivation is low, academic performance and academic progress will definitely decrease, so one of the duties of teachers is to take the problem of frustration and low motivation of students seriously in the classroom and before doing anything else create the necessary motivation in students; If they succeed in this way, they will pave the path for teaching and learning in students. In addition, the following are recommended to colleagues:

- Taking into account the individual differences of learners when designing educational activities and in the course of teaching
- Using new, creative and modern methods in English language teaching
- Coordinating the level of expectations with the level of ability and talent of the learners
- Using verbal encouragements such as well done, nice job, etc.
- Adapting the level of difficulty of the assignments to the level of learning and the ability of the learner
- Presentation of instructional materials from simple to difficult.

Suggestion to Dear Parents

Respected parents are also recommended to provide the necessary conditions and platform for students to study by providing a peaceful environment at home and preparing appropriate educational books. Also, they should support the progress of students in academic and moral fields, and they should maintain their relationship with the teaching staff of the school and always follow up on the academic status of their children in the school. Another important point that they must pay attention to is that they should avoid comparing, humiliating and blaming their children's unfavorable performance and instead of these cases, they should encourage and motivate their positive actions in academic fields. (Shabani, 2016).

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